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Accelerating Economic Growth : Trends and Way Forward

- ▶ Infrastructure Development
- ▶ Health Issues and Economic Growth
- ▶ Revival of Agriculture and Rural Area Development

72. **The Landscape of The Risk Factors For Non Communicable Diseases In India – An Epidemiological Review**
Manchala Sridevi..... 829

73. **Covid-19 and Migrant Workers : Challenges and Strategies**
Devendra Vishwakarma..... 844

74. **An Analysis of Impingement of COVID-19 on Indian Economic Development**
Parul Verma..... 854

75. **Indian Economy at Crossroads: An Impact Analysis of Covid-19 Pandemic**
Jomon Mathew..... 868

76. **Performance of Integrated Child Development Services In Health Care Delivery**
G.Rajaram
M. Kavitha..... 876

77. **Creating a Pathway from Rescue to Recovery, by Transformation and Economic Growth**
Madhubanti Dutta..... 888

78. **COVID-19, MSME Sector and Policy Responses in India**
Kabita Kumari Sahu..... 896

79. **Relationship between Health Care Expenditure and Economic Growth: A Causality Analysis using Co-integration Test**
Ashok Bhukta
Sudhakar Patra..... 905

80. **Pathways to Sustainable Development Goals and beyond-COVID-19 Strategies in India**
Vipin Chandran K P
Sandhya P..... 916

81. **Healthcare Vulnerability, Infrastructural Facilities and Economic outcome among Indian States: A comparative Study**
Sagarika
Dash & Manoj Kumar Das..... 930

82. **The Covid-19 and Reverse Migration in Rural Chhattisgarh**
Pragati Krishnan
Ravindra Brahme
Hanumant Yadav..... 941

83. **Impact of Covid-19 on Poverty And Inequality In India**
Rakesh Kumar Singh
Triloki Nath Tiwary..... 955

84. **Effect of COVID-19 on the Pharmaceutical Sector of India**
Aanchal Dagar
Qamar Alam..... 962

85. **Review of Health Status of Women in India with Special reference to Karnataka State First Author**
Jayamangala
Ravindra Kumar B..... 972

86. **Study on Socio-Economic Conditions of Labor for The Development of India**
Ram Eqbal Yadav..... 992

87. **Study on Health With Socio-Economic Conditions Among Rural Women**
Raj Kumar Yadav..... 998

88. **Impact of the COVID-19 on Different Sectors of Indian Economy–Application of Restricted Cubic Splines**
Velagala DMV Lakshmi
Akanksha Saxena..... 1003

Relationship between Health care and Economic Growth: A Causality analysis using Co-integration Test

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Abstract

This objective is to examine the relationship between health care expenditure and economic growth based on time series data from 1992 to 2020. They are GDP (Y) as a dependent variable, Public Health Expenditure (X_1) and Private Health Expenditure (X_2) as independent variables. The data of these three variables from 1992 to 2020 are collected from World Bank data base. The data are analyzed to determine the causality between Public Health Expenditure and Economic Growth in India as well as private health expenditure and Economic Growth (GDP) of India. The analysis is based on results of the Johansen Co-integration test. There is strong positive long-run relationship between India's health expenditure and GDP. Furthermore, the Granger causality test detected bi-directional causality from GDP to health expenditure. The Johansen test for co-integration is applied to find relationship between GDP (Y) as a dependent variable, Public Health Expenditure (X_1) and Private Health Expenditure (X_2). Since they are integrated of the same order, thus ensuring the condition to apply Johansen co-integration. From the study it is found that in our country, economic growth leads to higher public health expenditure as well as private health expenditure. Public health expenditure and private health expenditure are integrated into a different order. Hence, these two variables will not have a co integration relationship. The result of co integration between per capita domestic income and per capita planned expenditure rejects the hypothesis of the existence of a long-run relationship between these two. Regarding economic growth to public health expenditure and private health expenditure, in both these cases, the probabilistic values are less than 5% in the case of all four lags, as the result, showing the significant value leads to reject the null hypothesis. So there is a causality relationship from economic growth to both public and private health expenditure. Finally, it can be said that in our country, economic growth leads to higher public health expenditure as well as private health expenditure.

On long-run causality, there should be some policies implication regarding economic growth leads to more public health expenditure for the sustainable and strong health infrastructure in India. Again in the short-run bidirectional causality between private and public health expenditure and economic growth result implies more to more investment in the health sector can lead to economic growth in the long run. Thus we may conclude that the growth of planned health expenditure overtime period may have occurred due to other reasons than to increase in per capita income of the country. The study found that there is no short-run causality running from public health expenditure to GDP. There is no long-run equilibrium relationship between per capita planned expenditure and per capita domestic income in the case of India. This implies that an increase in health expenditure since 1980

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has no relation with an increase in income. This means that India represents an example of a developing economy where the size of health expenditure expands in the process of economic transformation.

Keywords: *Co-integration test, Causality, Gross Domestic Product, Health care expenditure, Long run.*

INTRODUCTION

The relationship between Healthcare Expenditure and Economic Growth has been a continuing issue in economics and public finance literature on both theoretical and empirical levels. In this context, we have two main strands of theories that explain the long-run relationship between Government health Expenditure and Economic Growth. In contrast to it, the Keynesian hypothesis considers Government Expenditure as an exogenous variable that influences Economic Growth. The direction of causality between Government Expenditure and Economic Growth is important for policy implications (Mehta, 2017). The major study shows an increase in public expenditure leads to an increase in economic growth in the long-run and supports the Keynesian approach. In the short-run economic growth causes rise in public expenditure and a rise in public expenditure creates inflationary pressure in the economy. Both in the short-run and long-run inflation adversely affect economic well-being. In the short-run public expenditure fails to create the growth effect because of the inflationary effects of public spending which winds up the growth effect (Maurya & Singh, 2017). The earlier findings on health–wealth linkages suggest that along with the adoption of policies aiming to increase the health standards, other growth-enhancing programmes and policies should be introduced to have a larger impact on health standard as well as overall human development. Show the direction of the relationship between economic growth and health standard at the state level, that is, whether there is unidirectional causality or bidirectional causality between them (Verma & Usmani, 2019). Nexus between Health Care Expenditure and economic growth exist in SAARC countries because there is an indirect effect on health via improvements inherent in changes in lifestyle (Khan et al., 2016). The income elasticity is below the unity implying that health expenditure is a necessity rather than a luxury good at the state level. On the contrary, the ageing index, the mortality rate, the birth rate and the resident population for generic physicians are in- significant (Magazzino & Mele, 2012). The findings of this study may be helpful for the policy-makers to amend the existing policies and budgetary allocation for the health care sector and education sector respectively (Yun & Yusoff, 2015). Total government expenditure, about 8% is spent on health. This estimate was from the World Health Organization's (WHO's) global health observatory data repository which is based on national health accounts. For the government spent about 1104543 million

rupees on health (central and states combined). This is about 3.68% of the total government expenditure of 30037588 million rupees and not 8% as quoted (Grover, 2015). Many of the studies find that there is a strong and positive correlation between the gross domestic product (GDP) of a country and national expenditure on health care (HCE) (Asif & Sultan, 2013). These research findings would serve as effective policy instruments to measure the progress towards universal health coverage among the states of India (Behera D. K, 2017). Many women died at home without going to a health care facility (Pradhan J. & Behera S., 2020). Capital accumulation is a major component of growth and healthcare expenditure is a way to increase capital accumulation (Bedir, 2016).

This study attempts to analyze the issue of inclusive growth in India in terms of public expenditure on healthcare and domestic income using co-integration analysis. Using Johansen's cointegration relationship, the present study examined has the existence of a long-run relationship between per capita domestic income and per capita planned expenditure on health or total expenditure on health (Asif & Sultan, 2013). The short-run dynamics of the variables show that the flow of causality runs from GDP to health care expenditure (Cosimo Magazzino, 2011).

METHODOLOGY

In this study, three variables are taken into the consideration. They are GDP (Y) as a dependent variable, Public Health Expenditure (X_1) and Private Health Expenditure (X_2) as independent variables. The data of these three variables from 1992 to 2020 are collected from World Bank data base. The data are analyzed to determine the causality between Public Health Expenditure and Economic Growth in India as well as private health expenditure and Economic Growth (GDP) of India. Before analyzing the causal relationship between Public Health Expenditure and Economic Growth data has been transformed into natural logarithms, and then the possible existence of unit roots in the data is examined. The Stationarity of each series is investigated by employing the Augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test. The number of lagged differences included is determined by the Schwarz Information Criterion and Akaike Information Criteria. Further, proceed with the VAR lag order selection criteria to choose the best lag length for the VAR time series model to examine the Granger Causality test for all the series is performed. Johansen co-integration test is also applied to test for co-integration. The basic empirical investigation has two purposes. The first one is to examine the long-run relationship between Public Health Expenditure and Economic Growth while the second is to examine the short-run dynamic causal relationship between Public Health Expenditure and Economic Growth. The basic testing procedure requires three steps. The first step is to test whether the variables contain a unit root to confirm the Stationarity of each

variable. This is done by using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller tests (ADF). In the second step, for the existence of a long-run co-integrating relationship between the variables. This is done by the use of the Johansen co-integration test. Finally, in the last step, if all variables are integrated of the same order and co-integrated then short-run and long-run causality test can be computed using the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) method suggested by Engle and Granger. To summarising, step one is the Unit Root Test, step two is Lag Selection, step three is the Co-integration test, and the last step is VECM.

Hence the majority of cases are showing 4 lags. So here 4 lags are selected. In each criterion except LR, the lower the value better the lag selection principle is there.

HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY

Hypothesis-1 Null hypotheses- H0: Public Health Expenditure does not Granger Cause Economic Growth.

Alternative hypotheses-H1: Public Health Expenditure does Granger Cause Economic Growth.

Hypotheses-2 Null hypothesis- H0: Economic Growth does not Granger Cause Public Health Expenditure.

Alternative hypotheses-H1: Economic Growth does Granger Cause Public Health Expenditure.

Since the time series are co-integrated then we will go for appropriate estimations, that is, VAR or VECM (Vector Error Correction Methods). If not, then we will go for only VECM.

VECM (VECTOR ERROR CORRECTION METHODS)

Already we have the lag selection criteria and co-integration test. Now we will move to Vector Error Correction Criteria. So the guideline is if the variables are co-integrated or have a long-run association ship then we can run restricted VAR, I.e., the VECM model. But if the variables are not co-Integrated, we cannot use the VECM model rather we shall run unrestricted VAR. So here all the three variables are co-integrated, we can go for the VECM model.

Table-1 Co-integration Model

Vector Error Correction Estimates	
Included observations: 24 after adjustments	
Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []	
Co integrating Eq:	CointEq1
Y(-1)	1.00
X1(-1)	-81.95

	(9.00)
	[-9.10]
X2(-1)	-4.18
	(4.14)
	[-1.01]
C	-167.71

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

So there are two issues.

1. Long-run causality

2. Short-run causality

LONG-RUN CAUSALITY:

If this $C(1)$ is negative in sign and significant, then we can say that there is a long-run causality running from X_1 and X_2 to Y . So here the p-value of $C(1)$ is 0.4824 which is more than 5%. This is not significant. Meaning that there is no long-run causality running from Public expenditure and private expenditure to GDP. And the second issue is as follow

SHORT RUN CAUSALITY:

Here the coefficients of all the four lags of 1st independent variable that is public health expenditure are $C(6)$, $C(7)$, $C(8)$, $C(9)$. So if they are zero ($H_0=C(6)=C(7)=C(8)=C(9)=0$), it can be said there is no short-run causality running from Public expenditure to GDP. So to check it we will go to the **Wald test (Wald Chi-Squared Test)**

WALD TEST (WALD CHI-SQUARED TEST)

The null hypothesis for the test is some parameter = some value. For example, here I study if GDP is affected by public health expenditure. "GDP" would be my parameter. The value could be zero (indicating that GDP is affected by public health expenditure). If the null hypothesis is rejected, it suggests that the variables in question can be removed without much harm to the model fit. That is illustrated in table-2.

Table-2 Wald Test:

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
F-statistic	0.63	(4, 10)	0.65
Chi-square	2.51	4	0.64
Null Hypothesis: $C(6)=C(7)=C(8)=C(9)=0$			
Null Hypothesis Summary:			
Normalized Restriction (= 0)		Value	Std. Err.
C(6)		116.57	100.46

C(7)	140.76	115.18
C(8)	-115.17	94.20
C(9)	-18.63	50.04

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Source: Computed by Author by Using E-Views software

Here the p-value is 64.20%, which means the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. Hence $C(6)=C(7)=C(8)=C(9)=0$. Therefore, there is no short-run causality running from public health expenditure to GDP.

And the second independent variable, i.e, private health expenditure, which does cause GDP or not. Here the coefficient of all lags of these variables in C (10), C (11), C (12), C(13). Again the null hypothesis is $C(10)=C(11)=C(12)=C(13)=0$. Where this is zero or not I check the Wald test.

Table-3 Wald Test:

Test Statistic	Value	df	Probability
F-statistic	0.71	(4, 10)	0.60
Chi-square	2.83	4	0.59

Null Hypothesis: $C(10)=C(11)=C(12)=C(13)=0$

Null Hypothesis Summary:

Normalized Restriction (= 0)	Value	Std. Err.
C(10)	28.56	31.12
C(11)	3.24	17.17
C(12)	-10.08	21.50
C(13)	-3.80	26.07

Restrictions are linear in coefficients.

Source: Computed by Author by using eviews software

The p-value is 58.69% which makes the null hypothesis accepted. This means all the coefficients of X2 variables are zero. Therefore, there is no short-run causality from private health expenditure to GDP. Hence, it can be said that no Long-run or short-run causality is running from private health expenditure and public health expenditure to GDP.

ESTIMATION AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS

The Johansen test for co-integration is applied to find relationship between GDP (Y) as a dependent variable, Public Health Expenditure (X_1) and Private Health Expenditure (X_2). Since they are integrated of the same order, thus ensuring the condition to apply Johansen co-

integration. Since the result of VAR analysis is also affected by the number of lag period, appropriate lag is selected based on Akaike information criteria (AIC).

Thus, to estimate the long-run relationship between the variables has applied the Johansen co-integration. The result is summarized in table-3a and 3b. Table 3a provides the result of trace statistics. Starting with the null hypothesis of no co-integration among the variables, trace statistics is 15.25741 which is less than the 5 % critical value of 15.49471. Thus we accept the null hypothesis of no co-integration among these variables at 5 per cent. In this table, we again find that the Maximum Eigen value is less than the critical value for no co-integration and accept at no co-integration at a 5 per cent level of significance. Thus, we may conclude that per capita planned expenditure and per capita domestic income are not co-integrated, and hence, there is no long-run equilibrium relationship between per capita planned expenditure and per capita domestic income in the case of India. This implies that an increase in health expenditure since 1980 has no relation with an increase in income. This may be due to some other socio-economic or political factors.

Table-4: Lag Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-272.92	NA	774454.8	22.07	22.22	22.11
1	-193.95	132.66	2895.05	16.48	17.06	16.64
2	-183.82	14.59	2745.71	16.39	17.41	16.67
3	-165.29	22.23	1410.66	15.62	17.09	16.03
4	-133.97	30.07*	287.70*	13.84*	15.04*	14.36*

Source: Computed by Author using E-views (* indicates lag order selected by the criterion, LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level), FPE: Final prediction error, AIC: Akaike information criterion, SC: Schwarz information criterion, HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion)

So here out of all lag selection criteria, all are showing four lags. Hence, the majority of cases are showing 4 lags. So here 4 lags are selected. In each criteria except LR, the lower the value better the lag selection principle is there.

JOHANSEN'S TEST OF COINTEGRATION

Table-5 : Unrestricted Cointegration (Trace Test)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen Value	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Values	Prob.*
None	0.52	29.97	29.80	0.05
At most 1	0.31	10.17	15.49	0.27

Note: Test was performed using E-views

Trace statistics show no co-integration at 5 per cent critical level.

Mackinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values.

Table-6 Johansen’s Test of Cointegration

Johansen’s Test of Cointegration (Maximum Eigen value Test)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigen Value	Maximum Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Values	Prob.*
None	0.52	19.80	21.13	0.07
At most 1	0.31	10.13	14.26	0.20

Note: Test was performed using E-views

Trace statistics show no co-integration at a 5 % critical level.

Mackinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values.

JOHNSEN’S CO-INTEGRATION ANALYSIS

There are three variables such as public health expenditure, private health expenditure and GDP (current US\$). Now but there is a precondition for running a co-integration model, and that is variable must be non-stationary at level but when I convert all the variables into first difference then they become stationary. Before the assume that our two independents are non-stationary at level but when to convert them into first difference, then they become stationary, but the public health expenditure is stationary at the second difference.

Using Johnsen’s co-integration relationship, the paper has examined the existence of a long-run relationship between public health expenditure and GDP, and private health expenditure and GDP. The result shows that public health expenditure and private health expenditure are integrated into a different order. Hence, these two variables will not have a cointegration relationship. The result of cointegration between per capita domestic income and per capita planned expenditure rejects the hypothesis of the existence of a long-run relationship between these two. Thus we may conclude that the growth of planned health expenditure overtime period may have occurred due to other reasons than to increase in per capita income of the country.

Table-7 Panel Causality Analysis Results

The way of the Relationship	Lag	Probability Values	Results
Public Health Expenditure → Economic Growth	1	0.74	Public Health Expenditure does not Cause Economic
	2	0.62	
	3	0.56	

	4	0.42	Growth
Economic Growth → Public Health Expenditure	1	0.04*	Economic Growth is the main cause of Public Health Expenditure
	2	0.00*	
	3	0.00*	
	4	0.00*	
Private Health Expenditure → Economic Growth	1	0.00*	Private Health Expenditure does not cause Economic Growth
	2	0.23	
	3	0.69	
	4	0.51	
Economic Growth → Private Health Expenditure	1	0.00*	Economic Growth is the main of Private Health Expenditure
	2	0.00*	
	3	0.00*	
	4	0.01*	

Source: Computed by Author (* mark indicates significant)

Table-7 shows that there is no causality relationship between public health expenditure to economic growth. Due to the main reason for having all lag values are greater than 0.05. This scenario is also similar concerning the relationship between private health expenditure to economic growth. As a result the null hypothesis which is “no causality relationship” is accepted. Moreover, in the case of private health expenditure to economic growth, the first lag showing a significant probability value that is less than 5% but except for the first leg, the rest four lags are greater than 5%. Hence null hypothesis “no causality relationship” cannot be rejected.

Regarding economic growth to public health expenditure and private health expenditure, in both these cases, the probabilistic values are less than 5% in the case of all four lags, as the result, showing the significant value leads to reject the null hypothesis. So there is a causality relationship from economic growth to both public and private health expenditure. Finally, it can be said that in our country, economic growth leads to higher public health expenditure as well as private health expenditure.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Any Econometric study will have many limitations, even when the models are rigorously specified. Our study also may suffer from such limitations which are mentioned below.

1. There may be some important independent variables that are not included in the model, which may deprive the model of its practical significance.

2. The models are selected in this study based on the statistical criterion of explanatory power. Some models having higher explanatory power may not have sound theoretical underpinning.

3. The conclusion derived only for the Indian context for the particular reference period 1992 to 2020. Therefore generalizations based on the conclusions derived here may not be valid for the other countries or for the other time period.

FINDINGS

Public health expenditure and private health expenditure are integrated into a different order. Hence, these two variables will not have a cointegration relationship. The result of cointegration between per capita domestic income and per capita planned expenditure rejects the hypothesis of the existence of a long-run relationship between these two. Thus we may conclude that the growth of planned health expenditure overtime period may have occurred due to other reasons than to increase in per capita income of the country. There is no long-run equilibrium relationship between per capita planned expenditure and per capita domestic income in the case of India. This implies that an increase in health expenditure since 1980 has no relation with an increase in income. This may be due to some other socio-economic or political factors.

SUGGESTIONS

On long-run causality, there should be some policies implication regarding economic growth leads to more public health expenditure for the sustainable and strong health infrastructure in India. Again in the short-run bidirectional causality between private and public health expenditure and economic growth result implies more to more investment in the health sector can lead to economic growth in the long run.

CONCLUSION

In this study, we have examined the relationship between public health expenditure and economic growth for India during the period 1992 to 2020. The empirical result reveals that there is no long-run co-integrating relationship between Government Health Expenditure and Economic Growth in India. But in the short-run unidirectional causality is running from Economic Growth to Government Health Expenditure. It means in the short-run Economic Growth leads to Government Health Expenditure in India.

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